

TYPICAL MIMIC EXPRESSIONS OF UZBEK NATION

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Annotation: This thesis is devoted to the study of the mimetic expressions typical of the Uzbek people and their cultural, social and linguistic characteristics. Mimic expressions are an important part of national culture as a means of conveying a person's inner feelings and mood through facial expressions. During the study, the types of mimetic expressions common among the Uzbek people, their meaning, use in social situations and their specific aspects in comparison with other cultures were analyzed. This thesis is of great importance for studying the non-verbal means of communication of the Uzbek people and including them in linguistic research.

Keywords: Mimic expressions, Uzbek culture, non-verbal communication, facial expressions, national identity, emotions, social situations, linguistics, folk culture, means of expression.

Introduction.

Mimic expressions, which are one of the important parts of human communication, are a means of expressing emotions and mood through the movement of facial muscles. Mimic expressions are one of the elements of non-verbal communication that complement speech and sometimes independently express meaning, and they reflect the inner world of a person. Mimic expressions characteristic of the Uzbek people demonstrate the unique aspects of national culture and traditions. For example, emotions such as joy, sadness, surprise or discontent are directly conveyed through facial expressions.

To date, the study of the cultural and linguistic characteristics of mimic expressions in linguistics and sociology is of great importance. The fact that the mimic expressions characteristic of the Uzbek people and their special place in comparison with other cultures indicates the relevance of the research. This thesis aims to analyze the culture of facial expressions of the Uzbek people from a linguistic and social perspective, and to highlight their national specific aspects.

Main part

Features of facial expressions typical of the Uzbek people:

In Uzbek culture, facial expressions are manifested as a means of directly reflecting the emotional state. For example, a smile is perceived as a sign of sincerity and warmth, while frowning indicates sadness or discontent. These expressions are considered a part of culture associated with traditions and national values.

The role of facial expressions in social situations:

In different social environments, the facial expressions of the Uzbek people are manifested in different ways. While facial expressions are limited in a formal environment, in informal situations they are free and take on a form that more clearly expresses emotions. For example, when greeting, a sincere smile and an expression of hospitality are visible on the face.

When greeting, many Uzbeks express their greeting by placing their hands on their chests, which means they are placing their hands on their hearts and also means "I greet you with all my heart." It should be noted that Uzbeks are very polite.

Linguistic and cultural characteristics:

Although the facial expressions of the Uzbek people have some similarities in linguistic terms, they are distinguished by their distinctive features from other cultures. For example, widening the eyes is used as an expression of surprise, which may have a different meaning in other cultures. In particular, our traditions have led to the emergence of various gestures and facial expressions. Placing the hand on the chest also expresses respect for those around them.

Comparison of facial expressions with other cultures:

When comparing the facial expressions of the Uzbek people with Eastern and Western cultures, there is a uniqueness in expressing some emotions. For example, a modest smile among Uzbeks expresses respect, while a strong smile in the West indicates more social openness. While eating food silently among Uzbeks indicates civility, in some Eastern countries eating with a loud sound expresses respect for the person who prepared the food. This section aims to study the deep meaning of national culture and emotions through facial expressions characteristic of the Uzbek people.

Conclusion.

Facial expressions characteristic of the Uzbek people are an integral part of national culture, and they are important in expressing a person's inner feelings and ensuring clarity in communication with others. The study shows that facial expressions are closely connected

with the traditions, values, and social life of the Uzbek people. They reflect the emotional world and cultural characteristics of the people.

The thesis analyzes the role and importance of conveying emotions through facial expressions in various social situations. Also, the facial expressions of the Uzbek people are studied in comparison with other cultures, revealing their unique aspects. The results show that national culture and linguistic identity play a decisive role in determining the content of facial expressions.

This study lays the foundation for a deeper study of facial expressions and nonverbal communication in Uzbek linguistics. In the future, a more in-depth analysis of facial expressions and their similarities or differences with other cultures from a linguistic and psychological perspective should be considered one of the important scientific tasks. Thus, the facial expressions characteristic of the Uzbek people once again confirm the richness of Uzbek culture and their importance in communication between people.

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